

Additional Appendix to "Photometric Study of Hot Algol-Type Binaries Showing Long Cycles"

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ABSTRACT

Context. Double Periodic Variables (DPVs) are hot Algol-type interacting binary systems that exhibit both an orbital and a long photometric cycle. The origin of the latter may be related to cyclic structural changes in the accretion disc surrounding the gainer star, driven by a variable mass transfer rate. If this is the case, changes in the orbital light curve would be expected throughout the long cycle.

Aims. We conducted a detailed photometric analysis of the light curves of 134 Large Magellanic Cloud (LMC) DPVs to investigate variations in the morphology of the orbital light curves as a function of the long-cycle phase.

Methods. We disentangled the two photometric cycles from the Optical Gravitational Lensing Experiment (OGLE) *I*-band light curves for the studied systems. We thus compared the orbital light curves at opposite long-cycle phases, investigated the stability of the long period, and analysed the residuals of the disentangling process to search for significant frequencies above a 1% False Alarm Probability (FAP) threshold.

Results. We confirm that OGLE-LMC-DPV-097 and OGLE-BLG-ECL-157529 are the DPVs that exhibit the most extreme changes in their orbital light curves throughout the long cycle. By comparison, around 50% of the sample exhibits moderate morphological variations, particularly around orbital phase 0.5, likely associated with structural changes in the accretion discs. In addition, we identified 18 DPVs with variable long periods, including 10 new cases. In some of them, the long period either increases or decreases continuously over time. For the first time, we found DPV systems alternating between both behaviours at different epochs. Moreover, we detected frequencies in the residuals that could be directly related to changes in the morphology of the orbital curves. Finally, some previously reported frequencies disappear when a variable long period is taken into account.

Key words. stars: eclipsing binaries - stars: variables: general

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Appendix B: Supplementary figures for Sec. 4.2

This appendix presents the complementary figures for 17 of the 18 DPVs identified as exhibiting long-cycle period variability, as discussed in Sec. 4.2 of the main article. The remaining system, OGLE-LMC-DPV-080, is shown in detail in Fig. 4 of the main text. For each object, we display: (i) the WWZ analysis showing the temporal evolution of the long-cycle period, (ii) the reconstructed long-cycle light curve assuming a constant period from the LMC DPV catalogue, and (iii) the improved fit obtained when adopting a variable long period during the disentangling process. These visualisations support the conclusion that accounting for a variable long period significantly reduces the residual scatter and better reflects the long-cycle modulation.

Fig. B.1. Left panel: Long-cycle photometry after removal of the orbital modulation, with WWZ analysis showing the period evolution over time. White dots with error bars mark the GLS-derived period within each time bin used for disentangling. Middle panel: Long-cycle light curve assuming a constant period from the LMC DPV catalogue. Right panel: Same as the middle panel, but using a variable long period during the disentangling (see Sect. 4.2).

Fig. B.1. continued.

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Appendix C: Supplementary figures for Sec. 4.4.

This appendix shows the GLS periodograms of the residuals for 17 DPVs with variable long-cycle periods, complementing the analysis presented in Sec. 4.4 of the main article. For each system, we compare the periodogram obtained using a constant long period (black line) with that obtained using a variable long period (blue line). As discussed in the main text, the additional frequencies reported in earlier studies tend to disappear when the variability of the long cycle is properly accounted for during the disentangling process.

Fig. C.1. The black line represents the GLS periodogram of the residuals after disentangling the light curve using a constant long period, as published in the LMC DPV catalogue. The title of each panel indicates the OGLE ID of the corresponding DPV. Black vertical lines indicate additional frequency peaks (the label and dashed vertical line correspond to the period of the most prominent peak). The blue line corresponds to the GLS periodogram of the residuals after disentangling using a variable long period, as adopted in this study. The horizontal grey line marks a FAP of 1%.